

As on 31-03-2020, the following data collection and data entry procedures are recommended in order to linking crops to their relatives into the knowledge base system.

Steps for data collection:

1. The general way is to find several sources mentioning of the crops. The sources may be review papers, databases and web articles. Data is search by using the scientific name of the crop to ensure the right crop is taken.
2. The ideal data to be searched is the proof of phylogenetic studies of a crop. This data may exist in research articles.
3. The steps might vary according to the creativity of data collectors, capacity and time limitation. In general, the more time spent on the data collection, the more information would be retrieved.

Steps for data entry:

1. There are four fields to be entered, three of them are meant to be compulsory for every record.

1.1 Crop (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the crop common name.
- Choose the **RIGHT** crop name in Crop ID. Since the common name is used in Crop ID, ensure to check the scientific name of the crop in the 'Crop Records' table.

1.2 Relative Crop (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the other crop that is closely related to the crop itself.
- Relative crops could be genetically related to each other, e.g. variety, cultivar, sub-species etc.
- Ensure there is evidence that the crops are related to each other, the evidence could be retrieved from any literature

1.3 Notes

- This field is to store other information which is related to the crop itself.

1.4 Metadata ID

- This field is to link the record to its metadata.
- One **MUST** create a Metadata record in 'Metadata' table before entering Metadata ID